

The Relationship between the Palaces and the Buddhist Temples in Rattanakosin Period: Study on Wat Rajadhivas Vihara

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Abstract : Aims of this research were to study the relationship between the Palaces (the Kings and the Royalty of the Chakri Dynasty) and the Buddhist temples including Wat Rajadhivas Vihara in Rattanakosin Period of Thailand with the purpose of creating knowledge for Thai lifelong learning, especially for Thai youth and children, and to create positive attitude on Nationalism, Buddhism and Monarchy of Thai people. The findings disclosed that the Palaces have had relationships with 33,902 temples, close relationship with 290 royal temples, and closer relationship with the 8 royal temples regarded as the "Temple of King Rama". Moreover, there are only 16 Royal temples including Wat Rajadhivas Vihara where the Chakri Kings present the annual royal Kathin robes to the monks by themselves. Wat Rajadhivas Vihara has always been restored under royal patronage and served as royal shrine like the 8 Temples of King Rama.

Keywords : Palaces, Buddhists Temples, Wat Rajadhivas Vihara.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014